

A Quantitative Analysis Of The Phatic Function Of Newspaper Photographs Of Violence

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Abstract

The paper consists of two sections. The first section goes into the concept of phatic communication as applied to visual messages and serves as the theoretical foundation for the second section. In the second section, a quantitative case study is discussed which involved scoring the phatic function of selected photographs of violence and then correlating these scores with the circulation in a South African daily over a three-year period (1990-1992). The results confirmed the working hypothesis that photographs of violence with a prominent phatic function correlate more strongly with circulation than those with an ill-defined phatic function.

Introduction

The focus of this article is on the phatic (or contact) function of visual messages, which is a concept from the communication sciences that denotes the ability of an image to attract and maintain the interest of the viewer. In an attempt to illustrate the phatic function in everyday action in print journalism, a case study was conducted which aimed to test the working hypothesis that photographs of violence with a prominent phatic function correlate more strongly with circulation than those with an ill-defined phatic function.

Phatic communication

The term phatic communication was coined by the anthropologist Bronislaw Malinowski (1884-1942), referring to those parts of a communicative act which deal with establishing an atmosphere or maintaining contact, as opposed to those areas of communication which primarily involve the exchange of information, ideas or feelings. Phatic language, for example, usually includes comments on the weather, inquiries about health and other phrases which are useful to "oil" or maintain the channels of communication (Watson & Hill, 1993:139).

Van Aswegen & Steyn (1987:5) simply state that the phatic function, also called the social contact function (in Le Roux, 1979:89), involves the creation of contact with the receiver. Fourie (1980:101) calls images which perform a phatic function *blikvangers* (attention-getters), which either attract the attention of the receiver or maintain it, or both. The Flemish semiotician Peters (1978:58) notes that this function is more apparent in verbal communication than in visual communication. An example would be "Hello, can you hear me?" in a telephone conversation with a poor connection.

In a theoretical framework for the analysis of images formulated by Peters (1978), the phatic

function is listed as one of six distinct communicative functions which a visual message may perform. Peters took a model by the linguist Roman Jakobson (1960, for a discussion of Jakobson's work see Lechte, 1994:62) as a point of departure and merely adapted it to suit the analysis of images. The six communicative functions are the referential, poetic, expressive, conative, phatic and metalinguistic functions.

Stated briefly, an image performs a referential function when it provides a recognizable depiction of an existing object. An image performs an expressive function, when the intentions and attitudes of the communicator are expressed through it. The poetic function refers to the ability of an image to evoke aesthetic appreciation on the part of the viewer, and the conative function pertains to those aspects of the image that place the viewer in a better position to receive the represented message, such as a greatly enlarged view of a minuscule object. As mentioned above, the phatic function concerns the ability of an image to attract and maintain contact with the viewer. Lastly, the metalinguistic function describes those aspects of an image which provide additional clarifying information which usually occurs in another code. An example would be an arrow in a scientific photograph pointing at the area of interest.

Peters (1978:4) argues that the phatic function of an image may be articulated on three main levels. These are the material, the representational and the formal level. For example, a photograph may make contact with the viewer due to its extraordinary size (material aspect), due to the fact that the subject matter it depicts is of interest to the viewer (representational aspect, most people seem to be very interested in photographs of themselves), or because it has been overtly encoded by means of photographic technique, such as selective focus (formal aspect).

Peters (1978:59) also points out that the receiving situation may optimize or frustrate contact, which

includes the amount of time a viewer has to see the image as well as noise levels.

Case study

In an attempt to illustrate the phatic function in every day action in the print media, a case study was conducted which focused on the phatic function of photographs of violence in South Africa's largest selling daily, the *Sowetan*. As stated in the introduction, the study aimed to test the working hypothesis that photographs of violence with a prominent phatic function correlate more strongly with circulation than those with an ill-defined phatic function.

The *Sowetan* was chosen as the sample newspaper because it displayed a significant rise in circulation from 1990 to 1992 and also published many photographs of violence during the same period. According to the South African Audit Bureau of Circulation, the annual circulation increased by 10.3% from 1990 to 1991 and by 7.4% from 1991 to 1992. As the study was restricted to the period January 1990 to December 1992, it indirectly also throws some light on the question whether the inclusion of photographs of violence contributed towards the rise in circulation during those three years.

Admission criteria

The first step of the study was to formulate admission criteria for the published photographs of violence. The definition utilized leans heavily on the work of Krüger (1994), who investigated violence on German television. The definition is based on the observation that every act or occurrence of violence has distinct components. The assumption for the purpose of the study was that a photograph of violence must depict at least one of these components. The components are:

1. a perpetrator
2. the act or occurrence of violence
3. the victim
4. the damage caused
5. persons indirectly affected, such as bystanders
6. auxiliary aspects, such as a murder weapon, a getaway car.

Definition of violence

Violence was defined as the intentional induction as well as the unintentional occurrence of physical, psychological, material, social and ecological damage. The threat of violence, alleged, fictional, natural, accidental and socially legitimate violence were included, but causative and contributing factors, such

as poverty or mental illness, were excluded (for a discussion of such factors see Hoffmann and McKendrik, 1990:15)

The definition is a synthesis of violence definitions by Krüger (1994:73), which accommodates the widest scope of damage of the definitions reviewed, as well as definitions by Grebner, (1978:179), Gerson (1968:153), and Groebel & Gleich (1993:136).

Phatic function scoring criteria

A total of 733 photographs of violence were admitted to the study on the basis of the above stated definition and then scored in terms of their phatic function. The formulation of scoring criteria took the theoretical framework of Peters (1978) discussed above (i.e. that an image has material, representational and formal aspects) as the point of departure.

On the material level, image attributes such as the shape and the size of the image were scored. On the representational level, it was assumed that an image which contains many of the components of violence stated above, would be more likely to hold the attention of the majority of readers than an image which contains only one or only a few of these components. In other words, the more shocking the subject matter of the photograph is likely to be, the stronger is its envisaged phatic function. The scoring of the formal level concentrated on the way in which the phatic function of an image has been amplified by means of photographic technique.

For the purpose of the study a fourth scoring category was added. The layout aspect of the photographs of violence dealt with issues such as the placement of the image on the newspaper page. For example, a photograph placed at the top half of the newspaper page was assumed to attract the attention of the reader more easily than one on the bottom half of the page and consequently received a higher score.

The 33 scoring criteria for the material (M), representational (R), formal (F) and layout (L) aspects utilized are listed in Figure 1.

The study was in effect a content analysis in the sense that the scoring procedure was restricted to the manifest content of the images, or their denotative level of meaning. Possible connotations and associations were not scored (for a discussion of denotative, connotative and other levels of meaning see, amongst others, Barthes, 1973; Webster, 1980; Burgin, 1990; Pettersson, 1995).

Scoring was also restricted to the image itself and the (verbal) phatic function of the caption was not assessed.

In order to test the reliability of the scoring

Figure 1
PHATIC FUNCTION SCORING CRITERIA

Criterion	Option	Score	Criterion	Option	Score
M1. Dimension	a. <8x12 cm b. >8x12 & <12x17cm c. >12x17 cm	0.0 0.5 1.0	R14. Is a person pointing at someone /thing?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
M2. Chromaticity	a. b&w b. colour	0.0 1.0	R15. Does the situational light accentuate shape/form/texture?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
M3. Shape of image frame	a. rectangular b. non-rectangular	0.0 1.0	F1. Camera position	a. eye level b. non-eye level	0.0 1.0
M4. Is at least 75% of the image area dominated by a single tone or hue?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0	F2. Is the depth of field overtly manipulated?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R1. Is a perpetrator depicted?	a. none b. one c. more than one	0.0 0.5 1.0	F4. Is the contrast overtly manipulated?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R2. Is the act/occurrence of violence depicted?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0	F5. Is the framing or cropping of the image overtly unusual (e.g. a portrait with only one eye in the frame)?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R3. Is a victim depicted?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0	F6. Is the subject matter overtly distorted?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R4. Is an auxiliary aspect (e.g. weapon) depicted?	a. none b. one c. more than one	0.0 0.5 1.0	F7. Is the lighting overtly manipulated?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R5. Is an indirectly affected person depicted?	a. none b. one c. more than one	0.0 0.5 1.0	F8. Is movement emphasized (e.g. panning, freezing of action)?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R6. Is damage depicted?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0	F9. Is there an overt pattern (e.g. image grain or video monitor pattern)?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R7. Which type of damage is depicted or referred to?	a. physical b. material c. social d. psychological, ecological	1.0 0.6 0.3 0.3	F10. Is the colour overtly manipulated?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R8. Is the violence fictional or real-life?	a. fictional b. real-life	0.0 1.0	L1. Is the photograph on the front page?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R9. What is the status of the perpetrator(s) (if applicable)?	a. alleged b. convicted	0.0 1.0	L2. Are there other photographs on the same page or double-page spread?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R10. Is the violence natural or man-made?	a. natural e.g. a forest fire b. man-made	0.0 1.0	L3. Is the photograph part of a picture essay?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0
R11. Is the violence intentional or accidental?	a. accidental b. intentional	0.0 1.0	L4. On which (vertical) half of the page is the image placed?	a. top half b. middle c. bottom half	1.0 0.5 0.0
R12. Is the violence socially legitimate or criminal?	a. legitimate b. criminal	0.0 1.0			
R13. Is an attention-grabbing facial expression depicted?	a. yes b. no	1.0 0.0			

Key:
M = Material aspect
R = Representational aspect
F = Formal aspect
L = Layout aspect

mechanism, an initial list of scoring criteria was presented to a small group of practicing photojournalists based in Johannesburg for evaluation and comment. Taking their input into account, an amended list of 33 criteria (Figure 1) was used to score the selected photographs.

Correlation with circulation

The next step of the study was to correlate the phatic function scores with the circulation. As only monthly circulation figures were available from the South African Audit Bureau of Circulation, the number of photographs of violence with an above mean and with a below mean phatic function score per publishing day in a given month was correlated with the monthly circulation figure (i.e. average net sales per publishing day). The mean phatic function score of the 733 photographs was 11.2.

Pearson's correlation co-efficient (r) was used and interpreted by examining the squared value of r , which was then converted to a percentage (i.e. $\times 100\%$) indicating the partial influence of the phatic function of photographs of violence on the variance of the circulation.

The result obtained does not contradict the working hypothesis that photographs of violence with a prominent phatic function correlate more strongly with circulation than those with a weak phatic function.

Expressed as Pearson's r values, the strength of the association was found to be 0.11 (a partial influence of 1.29%) for photographs with a *below* mean phatic function score and 0.61 (a partial influence of 37.51%) for images with an *above* mean phatic function score.

Concluding discussion

Even though many factors shape the circulation of a newspaper, the results of this explorative study suggest that there is a strong likelihood that a cause-and-effect relationship exists between the inclusion of photographs of violence with a prominent phatic function and audience demand as measured by circulation. The results also support the assumption that the inclusion of photographs of violence contributed to the rise in circulation of the *Sowetan* from 1990 to 1992.

Several other interesting points also came to light in the course of the study. These include that almost all the photographs of violence analyzed were taken in Witwatersrand townships, which is where the majority of *Sowetan* readers stay. Consequently, it could be the case that the locale of the photographs contributed significantly towards the results obtained. Without

disregarding established theories about violence in the mass media, such as the catharsis theory (see Conradie & Botha, 1987:4), there is a possibility that the demand for photographs of violence might be based in part on the desire of readers to know which areas of their home town are "hotspots" where violence is likely to reoccur in order for them to plan a safe route home and to avoid the risk of entering a troubled area.

Another possible research question which arises from this study is whether it is possible to identify long-term trends in the correlation between photographs of violence and circulation which might indicate whether newspaper images are becoming increasingly traumatic in order to compensate for a desensitization amongst the readership towards attention-grabbing images of violence. In this regard, the view of Susan Sontag (1977:20) is instructive. She wrote:

"...the shock of photographed atrocities wears off with repeated viewings, just as the surprise and bemusement felt the first time one sees a pornographic movie wear off after one sees a few more. The sense of taboo which makes us indignant and sorrowful is not much sturdier than the sense of taboo that regulates the definition of what is obscene. And both have been sorely tried in recent years. The vast photographic catalogue of misery and injustice throughout the world has given everyone a certain familiarity with atrocity, making the horrible seem ordinary - making it appear familiar, remote ("its only a photograph") and inevitable. At the time of the first photographs of the Nazi camps, there was nothing banal about these images. After thirty years, a saturation point may have been reached. In these last decades, "concerned" photography has done as much to deaden conscience as to arouse it."

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